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1 Tracking the sun below the canopy:
2 assessing the diurnal pattern of light
3 interception in orchards and vineyards
4 by hemispherical imaging.

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1 Abstract:

2 Accurately monitoring the fraction of intercepted photosynthetically active radiation (fIPAR) is key
3 to optimizing irrigation and advancing precision agriculture. This is particularly relevant in
4 deciduous crops such as fruit tree orchards and vineyards where heterogeneous and discontinuous
5 canopies lead to diurnal variability in fIPAR, influencing water use efficiency. Traditional methods
6 for assessing fIPAR, such as those using optical sensors (e.g. ceptometers), are labour intensive and
7 limited by weather conditions. This study proposes a cost-effective photographic and video-based
8 approach for rapidly and reliably monitoring diurnal and daily fIPAR. The method involves
9 capturing hemispherical images at various locations within the alley between rows of trees,
10 followed by image processing to extract data relating to green vegetation and project the trajectory
11 of the sun. The method proposed for application to still and video images was compared to the use
12 of ceptometer measurements for a range of orchard and vineyard canopies, demonstrating a high
13 degree of agreement (R^2 values of 0.88 and 0.92) and consistency across a range of lighting
14 conditions. The findings highlight that, particularly when employing action cameras, this method
15 offers a practical, scalable, and labour-efficient alternative to traditional ceptometer-based
16 measurements. Its adaptability to orchard canopies and resilience under diverse weather conditions
17 and orchard configurations, including the presence of anti-hail nets, make it a valuable tool for
18 precision agriculture.

19 Keywords:

20 Light interception, fIPAR monitoring, Diurnal variation, Orchard management, Proximal sensing.

21

22

23 1. Introduction:

24 The extent of the crop canopy is a fundamental determinant of the water requirements of most crops
25 and particularly of tree crops (Allen & Pereira, 1998; Girona et al., 2011; Hsiao, 1990). Factors
26 such as tree dimensions, spacing, and three-dimensional structure vary significantly between farms
27 and are shaped by plantation design, trellis systems, management strategies, growth-limiting
28 factors, and growth vigour. These variations require accurate and scalable methodologies to assess
29 canopy size and structure for accurate orchard management within the framework of Precision
30 Agriculture.

31 Several parameters are commonly used to represent the extent of a canopy, including the fraction of
32 canopy cover (fCOVER), leaf area index (LAI), and fraction of intercepted or absorbed
33 photosynthetically active radiation (fIPAR and fAPAR, respectively) (Campillo et al., 2012; Gower
34 et al., 1999). Each parameter provides unique insights into the role of the canopy in light
35 interception, photosynthesis, and water use. Of these, fIPAR has gained the greatest prominence on
36 account of its ability to quantify the amount of sunlight intercepted by a canopy, which is directly
37 linked to water requirements (Auzmendi et al., 2011; Green et al., 2003; Marsal et al., 2014) and
38 crop productivity (Massonnet et al., 2008; Smith & Steduto, 2012; Wünsche et al., 1996).

39 Direct estimations of fIPAR are traditionally based on ceptometer and light-sensor measurements.
40 These devices are usually deployed in a predefined pattern, both above and below the vegetation
41 (Johnson et al., 2010), and at a given moment (instantaneous fIPAR). Measurements made with
42 ceptometers at around midday ($fIPAR_{\text{midday}}$) are assumed to provide a representative value of daily
43 fIPAR. These measurements can be repeated at different times in the season and provide a
44 quantitative basis for assessing the effects of pruning and/or other agricultural practices. The results
45 can be used to compare orchards with different crop varieties and/or tree spacings, to map the
46 spatial variability of different canopies, and to estimate the productive potential of a given orchard
47 (Lampinen et al., 2012).

48 However, under certain orchard training systems, measurements taken at midday may not represent
49 the entire day: measurements should, therefore, be taken at different times and over a wide range of
50 hours (Wünsche et al., 1995). For instance, Auzmendi et al. (2011) used a portable ceptometer to
51 manually measure instantaneous fIPAR once every 2 hours to trace the diurnal fIPAR curve.
52 Since taking multiple manual measurements with a portable ceptometer would be far too labour
53 intensive for routine application, an alternative could be to continuously record instantaneous
54 fIPAR, using a fixed arrangement of light-sensing bars. This could also allow the automated
55 adjustment of irrigation. Nevertheless, such setups would be too expensive for routine applications
56 on farms and could also hinder the movement of machinery in the orchard (Casadesús et al., 2011).
57 Alternatively, the diurnal curve of fIPAR could be estimated using relatively simple models
58 (Oyarzun et al, 2007) that require measurements of tree dimensions, such as a parallelepiped. These
59 models can be fed from UAV-based photogrammetry (Bellvert et al., 2021). However, tree shapes
60 often depart from a perfect parallelepiped and, as a result, such measurements tend to be inaccurate.
61 Image analysis can provide a practical way to assess canopy properties. Zarate-Valdez et al. (2015)
62 proposed a methodology for estimating light interception in walnut and almond orchards that is
63 based on overhead photography of tree shadows. A similar methodology was reported in Campillo
64 et al. (2008), but in that case it focused on a field-grown tomato crop and used downward-facing
65 photography. However, these methods provide only a measurement of midday fIPAR rather than a
66 daily aggregate from the diurnal curve.

67 Digital hemispherical photography (DHP), which involves capturing wide-angle and/or
68 hemispherical photos looking up through the plant canopy, has been widely used for the assessment
69 of many biophysical traits, especially in forests (Jonckheere et al., 2004; Baret et al., 2010; Fournier
70 & Hall, 2017). Improvements in camera technology and lens capabilities have made it possible to
71 obtain more precise images. Even so, orchards and forests are two different types of vegetation
72 stands. In orchards, where careful pruning and management practices are applied to optimize tree
73 and fruit growth, the leaf area is smaller than would be expected in natural forests and distributed

74 according to plantation patterns. While forests are relatively homogeneous in terms of their canopy
75 structure, having a continuous and dense distribution of foliage (Ross, 1981), orchards often exhibit
76 greater structural variability due to differences in tree spacing, canopy shape, and management
77 practices. This difference affects the estimation of biophysical traits, such as light interception, and
78 highlights the need for different approaches to DHP to obtain accurate assessments.

79 In this context, indirect methods for estimating biophysical parameters, and particularly light
80 interception, which rely solely on the Leaf Area Index or Leaf Area Density, such as the model
81 presented by Campbell & Norman (1998), may not be as reliable in orchards as in forests. LAI-
82 based estimations, which work well in forests, may underestimate fIPAR in orchards due to
83 differences in leaf area distribution and canopy architecture (Campbell & Norman, 1998; Ross,
84 1981). In the context of orchard canopies, previous studies have briefly examined similar
85 approaches based on digital photography. A comparative study of four methods for estimating light
86 interception was conducted by Wünsche et al. (1995); this involved the use of film cameras
87 equipped with hemispherical lenses.

88 The main objective of the present work was to analyse the performance and practical utility of an
89 approach based on the use of hemispherical images to assess the diurnal curve of the fraction of
90 intercepted PAR in tree crops and vines. The method consists of (1) taking samples in the tree
91 spacing between rows of trees, using photos or videos, to obtain a mosaic of upward-facing
92 hemispherical images of the canopy; (2) analysing the images by overlaying the calculated diurnal
93 solar trajectory on the segmented canopy of each image and; (3) aggregating data to obtain a diurnal
94 fIPAR curve for the whole tree spacing, including one half of the trees on either side of the
95 alleyway and the alleyway itself. This methodology was applied to images taken using a still
96 camera mounted on a self-levelling support and, in parallel to those from videos recorded using an
97 action camera held on a selfie-stick. The still camera setup, thanks to its stable mounting and
98 controlled positioning, allowed for more consistent image acquisition. In contrast, the action camera
99 offered a more flexible and low-cost alternative, with faster data collection but less control over

100 image alignment. The performance of both approaches was then evaluated by comparing their
101 outputs to measurements obtained through a standard ceptometer method.

102 2. Materials and Methods:

103 2.1. Methodological workflow:

104 **Procedure for image acquisition**

105 For both fixed camera pictures and action camera videos, the procedure consisted of recording a
106 collection of hemispherical upwards-looking images of the canopy, following a pre-defined pattern,
107 recording the area between two adjacent rows of trees. The camera was placed near the ground and
108 levelled to achieve a zenith view, with vertical axis of the images aligned parallel to the tree rows
109 (see Figure 1).

110

111 **Still Camera with self-levelling platform**

112 A D70 (Nikon, Tokyo Japan) reflex camera equipped with an AT-X 107 DX (Tokina, Tokyo,
113 Japan) fisheye zoom lens was mounted on a custom-made self-levelling support, which maintained
114 the camera in an upward zenithal view, regardless of the ground slope. The lens height was about
115 20 cm above the ground. The support, which had a base footprint of 50 cm x 50 cm, was manually
116 moved to different positions following a chessboard sampling pattern (Figure 1). Photos were taken
117 within the alleyway, at 100 cm intervals, covering the full distance between rows.

118

119 **Action Camera**

120 A HERO10 Black (GoPro, California, USA) action camera was mounted on a selfie stick for
121 mobile image acquisition. Sampling involved recording videos with the camera held upwards and at
122 approximately 20 cm from the ground, while following an on-the-go zigzag pattern between two

123 rows of trees that included at least three consecutive trees in each row (Figure1). Efforts were made
124 to keep the camera levelled and well-oriented and to move at a constant speed between the trees
125 during video recording to ensure uniform sampling. The video footage was subsequently divided
126 into individual frames (at a rate of 1 frame per second), which were treated similarly to the still
127 photograph images.

128

129

130 **Image Analysis**

131 Custom-made software was developed in Python for processing the images, using version 1.6 of the
132 OpenCV library (Bradski, 2000). In the case of the video images recorded with the action camera,
133 the first step in the processing workflow involved extracting individual frames from the video
134 footage. One frame per second was selected for image extraction, from the initial 60 frames per
135 second of video footage. Each image was a sample of the canopy. It included part of the
136 background, the projected sun path during the day, and the diurnal fIPAR curve at that precise
137 point.

138 The fIPAR curves corresponding to the different points in the sampling pattern were then integrated
139 to create a single diurnal curve for the whole canopy.

140

141 **Canopy segmentation from the sky background**

142 In each image, the pixels corresponding to the canopy were separated from the background using
143 thresholds based on a converted HSV (Hue, Saturation, Value) colour space.

144 The pixels considered to correspond to the canopy ($\text{canopy}_{\text{mask}}$) were determined by removing those
145 matching the colour of a blue sky ($\text{blue}_{\text{mask}}$) and those matching the colour of a cloud or an overcast
146 sky ($\text{lightgrey}_{\text{mask}}$) from the initial image.

$$147 \text{canopy}_{\text{mask}} = \text{whole_image} - \text{blue}_{\text{mask}} - \text{lightgrey}_{\text{mask}} \quad (\text{Eq.1})$$

148 Where:

149 canopy_{mask} includes all the pixels considered to correspond to part of the canopy; the whole_image
150 is the total set of pixels in the image; the blue_{mask} includes all the pixels whose hue falls within a
151 predefined range, from hue_{min} to hue_{max}, which in this work corresponded to values of 180 and 270,
152 respectively, on a scale from 0 to 360; lightgrey_{mask} includes all the pixels whose saturation is lower
153 than sat_{max}, and whose intensity is greater than intensity_{min}, which in this work corresponded to
154 sat_{max} = 20, and intensity_{min} = 60, on a scale from 0 to 100.

155 During the process of taking photographs and recording video during daylight, the presence of the
156 sun disk in the scene can produce regions where the colour values of the affected pixels are
157 overflowed and, hence, undetermined. We called these regions as *sun flares*. Pixels of these regions
158 are considered background, which is true in most cases. However, part of the actual canopy pixels
159 neighbouring those regions can be flared as well and then, eroded from the canopy region and
160 erroneously accounted as background. (Figure 2). The maximum impact of this issue was quantified
161 as the percentage of flared pixels in the sampled images.

162 Broad application of the method to different horticultural scenarios, must consider the possibility of
163 using anti-hail nets. In that case, support structures of various colours, including poles and bars,
164 may appear in the background when upward-facing images are taken. Tests of the method were
165 conducted under hail nets with different properties to determine whether the thresholds should be
166 specifically adapted to the properties of each anti-hail net.

167 **Projection of the diurnal path of the sun on the images**

168 On each image, a curve was traced representing the position of the sun at different times in the day.
169 This was based on the field of view of the cameras and the traced path of the sun in x and y pixel
170 coordinates. It was calculated using the geographical coordinates of the orchard, the day of the year,
171 the camera azimuth and the optical calibration of a hemispherical lens camera.

172 Firstly, the elevation of the sun and its azimuth were calculated for each hour of the day, based on
173 Allen & Pereira (1998). Figure 3 illustrates the two angles involved, from Masters (2004).

174 Based on the latitude (φ), longitude (L) and corresponding day of the year (DOY), the solar curve
 175 parameters are:

176 Declination of the sun, $\delta = 0.409 \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{365 * DOY} - 1.39\right)$ (Eq. 2)

177 Elevation of the sun, $h_s = \sin^{-1}(\sin \varphi \sin \delta + \cos \omega \cos \delta)$ (Eq. 3)

178 Sun azimuth angle, $\gamma = \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{-\cos \delta \cos \varphi \sin \omega}{\sin \delta - \sin \varphi \sin \omega}\right)$ (Eq. 4)

179 Solar time angle, $\omega = \frac{\pi}{12}[(t + 0.06667(L_z - L_m) + S_c) - 12]$ (Eq. 5)

180 $S_c = 0.1645 \sin(2b) - 0.1255 \cos(b) - 0.025 \sin(b)$ (Eq. 5.1)

181 Where: S_c is a seasonal correction for solar time in hours, t is the standard clock time in hours, L_z is
 182 the longitude of the centre of the local time zone in degrees, L_m is the longitude of the measurement
 183 site in degrees.

184 Secondly, the apparent path of the sun in the sky, represented by its hourly elevation and azimuth,
 185 was converted into a curve in the image and represented by a list of pixel coordinates.

186 Given the height (h) and the width (w) of the image, the elevation of the sun (h_s) and its azimuth (γ_s)
 187), the azimuth of the camera (γ_c) and calibrated conversion from pixel coordinates to corresponding
 188 camera and lens angles (α_c), the coordinates (x, y) of the position of the sun in the image were
 189 given by Eq. 6.

190 $\begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{w}{2} - x_i \\ \frac{h}{2} - y_i \end{pmatrix}$ (Eq. 6)

191 Where:

192 $\begin{pmatrix} x_i \\ y_i \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} r \sin(\gamma_s - \gamma_c) \\ r \cos(\gamma_s - \gamma_c) \end{pmatrix}$ (Eq. 6.1)

193 $r = \alpha_c \cos h_s$ (Eq. 6.2)

194

195

196

197 Determination of the diurnal fIPAR curve

198 The procedure assumed that fIPAR at a given time of day consists of two components. The beam
199 component depends on the fraction of canopy pixels located in the part of the image where the sun
200 is expected to appear at that specific time. The diffuse component depends on the overall fraction of
201 canopy pixels across the entire image. In each individual image, computation was made by defining
202 a series of rectangles that followed the path of the sun. Each of these represented the position of the
203 sun at a given time of day.

204 Two variables were calculated for each rectangle. Firstly, the beam fIPAR ($fIPAR_{beam}$), which was
205 dimensionless, determined as the fraction of canopy pixels compared to the total number of pixels
206 in the rectangle. Secondly, the quantity of potentially intercepted PAR at a given time, $PIR_{instantaneous}$,
207 on a clear day, was determined as shown in Eq. 7:

$$208 \quad PIR_{instantaneous} = fIPAR_{beam} * R_S * (1 - K_d) + fIPAR_{img} R_S * K_d \quad (Eq.7)$$

209 Where R_S is the expected solar radiation under a clear sky at the location in question, on the day of
210 the year and at the chosen time of day, $fIPAR_{img}$ is the fraction of canopy pixels for the total image,
211 and K_d is a coefficient that represents the fraction of diffuse radiation.

212 To simplify computation, the radiation regime chosen was that of clear sky, based on the theoretical
213 beam radiation proposed by Allen & Pereira, 1998:

$$214 \quad R_S = 0.75 R_a, \quad (Eq. 8)$$

$$215 \quad R_a = \frac{60}{\pi} G_s * d_r (\omega_2 - \omega_1) \sin \varphi \sin \delta \cos \varphi \cos \delta (\sin \omega_2 - \sin \omega_1) \quad (Eq. 8.1)$$

$$216 \quad d_r = 1 + 0.033 \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{365} n\right) \quad (Eq. 8.2)$$

217 Where:

218 R_a , in W/m^2 is the extraterrestrial radiation.

219 G_s is the solar constant ($1366 W/m^2$).

220 d_r is the inverse relative distance between the Earth and the Sun.

221 φ and δ , expressed in radians, are the latitude and the declination of the sun.

222 ω_1 and ω_2 are the solar time angles at the beginning and at the end of the period, expressed in
223 radians.

224 To account for the diffuse component of radiation when assessing the diurnal fIPAR, the fraction of
225 diffuse radiation, K_d , was assumed to be equal to 0.2, to simplify the computation. To allow visual
226 inspection of the process, the software saved a processed copy of each image, in which the
227 rectangles and the diurnal curves of $fIPAR_{beam}$ and $PIR_{instantaneous}$ were overlapped (Figure 4).

228 As commented above, the presence of sun flares in the scene may result in an underestimation of
229 the number of canopy pixels. To compensate this effect, a second series of rectangles was added,
230 which rarely contained sun flares. This symmetry corresponds to the pattern observed in the first
231 series of projected rectangles, assuming that canopy properties are similar on both sides of the East–
232 West axis.

233

234 **Converting diurnal curves to a daily fIPAR value**

235 For practical application, in many situations, using a single daily value that summarizes the diurnal
236 fIPAR curve could be more practical than using the curve itself. This value was calculated as shown
237 in Eq. 9.

238 After determining the diurnal curves of $fIPAR_{beam}$ and $PIR_{instantaneous}$ for all the individual images of
239 a given canopy, the completed curves are obtained by averaging the corresponding diurnal fIPAR
240 curves across images. All these calculations were carried out automatically using the algorithm that
241 was developed. In practice, it was a weighted average of the instantaneous fIPAR, where the
242 weights were provided by the R_s values at that time.

$$243 \quad fIPAR_{daily} = \frac{\sum R_s PIR_{instantaneous}}{\sum R_s} \quad (\text{Eq. 9})$$

244

245

246

247 **Camera Calibration**

248 Camera calibration consisted of establishing how each pixel in the image corresponds to a specific
249 observation angle. This relationship depends on the camera and lens used and is essential to
250 accurately project the sun's path onto the images. The dataset for calibrating each camera was
251 obtained by sampling a known pattern. This was carried out in lab, using the same lens and camera
252 combination options that were used in the field. Both the still camera and the action camera were
253 firmly mounted on tripods, aimed at a board marked with magnets positioned at precise, known
254 coordinates (see Figure 5).

255 This setup allowed us to calibrate the cameras by correlating their angles to these fixed reference
256 points (see Figure 6).

257 Magnets were organised on the board in a star configuration. Having magnets of different colours
258 facilitated the task of identifying them in the images and referring to their positions on the board.
259 (Fig. 2). Photographs and short videos were obtained with three different distances between the
260 board and the cameras to allow a varied range of angles.

261 For each picture or video frame, the viewing angle for each magnet was calculated as follows:

$$262 \text{ Angle} = \arctan\left(\frac{d_{magnet, center}}{d_{camera, board}}\right) \quad (\text{Eq.9})$$

263 Where:

264 $d_{magnet, center}$ is the distance in cm between the magnet and the centre of the board.

265 $d_{camera, board}$ is the distance in cm between the camera and the board.

266 The parameter to be calibrated was the slope of the relationship between the distance in pixels from
267 each magnet to the centre of the image and the viewing angle for each magnet. The combination of
268 cameras, lenses and settings produced different fields of view in the sampled images (Table 1).

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Table 1. Still and action camera configurations and FOV analysis

Camera	Lens model	Settings	Picture frames (height x width pixels)	Diagonal fov (degrees)	Horizontal fov (degrees)	Vertical fov (degrees)	Calibrated degrees/pixel
Still camera (Nikon d70)	Tokina Fisheye	Widest zoom, infinity focus	3008 x 2000	165	138	92	0.0458
Action camera (GoPro Hero 10)	Action Camera	“SuperView” Mode	5568 x 4176	>180	>180	141	0.0338
	Max Lens	“WideAngle” Mode	4000 x 3000	>180	173	130	0.0432

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275 2.2. Datasets:

276 To validate the methodology, two datasets were created and used. The first: Dataset 1, was obtained
 277 from a large and spatially heterogeneous vineyard located at Raimat, Lleida, Spain, where the
 278 canopies of four sites were analysed. These involved two grape varieties at two topographic
 279 locations, resulting in different vine development patterns: *Vitis vinifera* cv. Chardonnay-large, *Vitis*
 280 *vinifera* cv. Chardonnay-small, *Vitis vinifera* cv. Pinot-large and *Vitis vinifera* cv. Pinot-small.

281 fIPAR was sampled using a still camera under two different light conditions, corresponding to
 282 consecutive days: dawn, with overcast sky, and during the day with a cloudless sky. This was done
 283 to evaluate the consistency between the two sampling conditions. On the second day, instantaneous
 284 fIPAR was also measured, using a ceptometer (AccuPAR model LP-80; Decagon Devices Inc.,
 285 Pullman, WA, USA), at 2-hour intervals, from sunrise to sunset.

286 The second dataset: Dataset 2, was designed to compare the labour effort and accuracy of the fIPAR
 287 measurements obtained with each approach. To do this, hemispherical photographs were obtained
 288 with a still camera and hemispherical video footage was recorded with an action camera. Images
 289 were obtained in an apple orchard, a vineyard and an almond orchard, on three consecutive days
 290 (Figure 7).

291 On each day, measurements were taken at three points in time between two hours before and two
292 hours after solar noon. The datasets are summarized in Table 2.

293 Another extensive dataset, relating to the same apple orchard that was used for the second dataset,
294 was also acquired. This included fisheye images featuring canopies of various dimensions (large
295 and small) and different backgrounds (with clear and overcast skies and anti-hail nets of different
296 colours) to examine the influence that the background had on the assessment.

297 For the measurements made by a portable Ceptometer (AccuPAR model LP-80; Decagon Devices
298 Inc., Pullman, WA, USA), readings were taken in the tree spacing, between the rows of trees; and
299 from below, at different positions in the alleyway. About 30 readings were taken at 0.5 m intervals
300 (PAR_{below}), after recording the incident PAR (PAR_{total}). Instantaneous fIPAR was then calculated as
301 follows:

$$302 \quad fIPAR_i = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{PAR_{i_{below}}}{PAR_{total}} \quad (\text{Eq. 10})$$

303 Where N is the number of readings taken, both in the alleyway and below the trees.

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316 Table 2. Summary of orchard characteristics, sampling conditions, and data collection parameters
 317 for the different datasets.

Dataset	1		2	
Orchard	Vineyard (<i>Vitis vinefera</i>)	Apples (<i>Malus domestica</i>)	Vineyard (<i>Vitis vinefera</i>)	Almonds (<i>Prunus dulcis</i>)
cv.	Chardonnay (Large, small); Pinot (Large, small)	Golden Reinders	Chardonnay	Vairo
Location (ETRS89 coordinates)	Raimat (41° 40' N–0° 28' E)	Mollerusa (41° 63' N–0° 9' E)	Raimat (41° 40' N–0° 28' E)	Les Borges Blanques (41° 30' N–0° 51' E)
Tree Spacing	Chardonnay: 2 m x 3 m. Pinot: 1.7 m x 3 m	1.2 m x 3.6 m	1.7 m x 2.5 m	3.5 m x 5.5 m
Row orientation	12° east	4° west	6° east	30° east
Tree dimensions (height, width, depth)	Chardonnay Large: 2 m x 1m x 0.5 m. Chardonnay Small: 2 m x 0.7 m x 0.3 m Pinot Large: 1.7 m x 1.2 m x 0.7 m. Pinot Small: 1.7 m x 0.6 m x 0.3 m	3.2 m x 1.2 m x 0.6 m	1.7 m x 0.7 m x 0.5 m	3.5 m x 2.5 m x 1.3 m
Sampling DOY	203-204	108-109-110	150-151-152	199-200-201
Cloudiness	DOY 203 overcast at dawn; DOY 204 cloudless	Cloudless	Cloudless	Cloudless
Num photos/sampling	30	30-35	25-30	40-45
Seconds video/sampling	-	30-40	30-40	50-60
Cept measur. /Sampling	60 in the alley + 6 reference	30 in the alley + 5 reference		
Sampled trees	6	6	6	6

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323 **Statistical analyses**

324 JMP statistical software v17.2.0 (SAS Institute Inc., Cary, USA) was used in the analysis. It was
325 particularly used to examine the relationship between the diurnal curves derived from photographs
326 and to check how they corresponded to the ceptometer readings. The coefficient of determination
327 (R^2) was computed to quantify the strength of the relationships.

328 **3. Results:**

329 The accurate assessment of diurnal and daily fIPAR based on sampled photos and frames required
330 careful preprocessing. This began with camera calibration and checking the FOV of still and action
331 cameras and ensuring that conversion was possible. This was followed by an evaluation of the
332 canopy segmentation performance, which determined how effectively the plant and non-plant areas
333 could be distinguished. Once the segmentation had been validated, the ability of the algorithm to
334 capture diurnal fIPAR curves was assessed. Diurnal curves were computed for each photo and/or
335 video frame. The process consisted of analysing a series of instantaneous fIPAR values, which had
336 been calculated at 10-minute intervals throughout the day. To further refine the approach, a
337 comparison was made between the images obtained using still and action cameras.

338 **3.1. Camera calibration:**

339 The calibration results indicated a field of view of 165° for the still camera along the diagonal, with
340 narrower angles in the middle of the horizontal and vertical axes (Table 1). The field of view of the
341 action camera was notably wider, in both the video and photo modes, than that of the fisheye lens
342 (180° , as opposed to 165°), which made it possible to capture a broader range of the diurnal curve.
343 The action camera had different fields of view for its photo and video modes (Table 1). The video
344 mode exhibited a slightly narrower diagonal FOV compared to the photo mode, though both were
345 wider than that of the fisheye lens on the still camera. Despite this difference, the video mode was
346 more practical for field applications due to its capacity to record continuously, this simplified data

347 collection in the field. This continuous capture reduced the time spent repositioning the camera and
348 made it possible to carry out a more detailed spatial and temporal analysis of the canopy structure.

349 3.2. Canopy segmentation in individual images:

350 The approach previously described required segmentation of the images to distinguish between the
351 canopy and background. Overall, the classification of the pixels based on colour space Intensity-
352 Hue-Saturation (I, H, S) make it easy to distinguish the foreground from the sky background. The
353 sky typically ranges from blue under clear conditions to various shades of grey, depending on cloud
354 cover.

355 However, visual examination of the images showed that in some of the images taken during
356 daylight, some canopy pixels were misclassified as part of the background due to their overflow
357 values by the sun flares (Figure 1). This effect did not occur in images obtained at dawn, in which
358 the distinction between the canopy and the background was much clearer. This effect was less
359 evident for larger canopies, possibly because denser canopies prevented it. From a quantitative
360 perspective, the difference between the fIPAR values obtained from images at dawn and those from
361 images relating to sunlight hours were, at the most, around 3 % (Figure 8). The automated
362 segmentation of the images to distinguish between the canopy and background was evaluated in a
363 sample of images to characterize the margin of error. Special emphasis was placed on the influence
364 of bright sun flares on the images and in the classification of areas with high brightness.

365 Classic canopy assessments involving the use of hemispherical photography in forests, typically use
366 images obtained at dawn, or under overcast sky conditions. In such cases, pixels can be easily
367 classified based on the intensity of the colour component of each pixel. To sample canopies at
368 different times of day, we had to account for disturbances caused by sun flares and reflected light,
369 which can alter leaf appearance in certain areas. Understanding these effects was essential to ensure
370 accurate measurements. In both cases, the pixels in question were overexposed and, as a result,

371 there was insufficient colour information to allow a reliable classification based on pixel colour
372 alone.

373 For the sake of simplicity, overexposed pixels were not assigned as canopy. In the images analysed,
374 the canopies were viewed from below. The images obtained were mostly composed of leaves,
375 stems, and growing fruits, while parts of the trellis system, such as poles and wires, also appeared in
376 the foreground. For the purposes of this study, all these objects were considered as part of the
377 canopy. The background thresholding process was based on certain ranges of H, S, and I, and the
378 results obtained indicated that its parameterization could be applied across a wide range of
379 background conditions, including blue skies, skies with different degrees of cloud cover, and even
380 images that included the presence of greyish anti-hail nets. However, in the case of coloured anti-
381 hail nets, which were yellow in this case, it was necessary to slightly modify the thresholding
382 technique as the algorithm mistakenly classified them as within the acceptable colour range for the
383 canopy (Figure 9).

384 3.3. Validation of the diurnal pattern of light interception:

385 Diurnal fIPAR curves were measured with the proposed method for four vineyard canopies using
386 the still camera. The results were then compared to ceptometer readings collected throughout the
387 daylight hours. Each of the canopies analysed in this study showed a different, and distinct, diurnal
388 pattern of fIPAR. These could be clearly discerned by applying both the hemispherical imaging
389 approach and using ceptometers.

390 Overall, the continuous diurnal patterns of fIPAR obtained using hemispherical imaging tended to
391 match the discrete measurements recorded by ceptometers at different times of the day. R^2 values of
392 0.88 and 0.92, with mean square differences of 0.07 and 0.08, were respectively obtained for
393 hemispherical imaging sampled at daytime and dawn (Figure 10). The performance of the analysis
394 provided sufficient resolution to be able to distinguish between the diurnal patterns represented by
395 all the four examples included in this study. For practical applications in horticulture and irrigation,

396 knowing the exact fIPAR at a specific time is less important. Instead, it's more useful to have a
397 summary of how fIPAR changes throughout the day. This diurnal curve can provide a clearer
398 picture of canopy light interception during daylight hours. The results obtained showed that the
399 hemispherical imaging approach provided similar assessments of the diurnal fIPAR curves for
400 discontinuous canopies as ceptometer readings, but with a fraction of the labour required to obtain
401 them (Figure 11). The alignment between the instantaneous fIPAR values obtained from ceptometer
402 readings and those from photography was slightly better when the photographic images were taken
403 at dawn.

404 On the other hand, the instantaneous values shown on the diurnal curves of fIPAR calculated from
405 images corresponding to daylight hours were closely correlated with those calculated from images
406 corresponding to dawn. In all cases, R^2 was greater than 0.98 (Figure 12), showing a high
407 repetitiveness of the method, even with different lighting conditions. Nevertheless, the fIPAR
408 values calculated from images corresponding to daylight were slightly lower than those of images
409 corresponding to dawn. This difference was most noticeable around the time the photos were
410 captured, which fits with the commented issue of sun flares affecting pixels at the edge of the
411 canopy. The effect was slightly more pronounced in small canopies.

412 3.4. Still vs Action Camera:

413 The average time required to sample a canopy ranged: from 8 to 10 minutes, using a ceptometer;
414 from 10 to 12 minutes, using a still camera; and from 1 to 2 minutes, using an action camera. As
415 mentioned earlier, hemispherical imaging allowed us to capture a continuous diurnal pattern of
416 fIPAR. In contrast, the ceptometer only provided discrete fIPAR values at specific times. This
417 limitation was due to the short time window available for measurements. To build a complete
418 diurnal curve using the ceptometer, measurements would need to be repeated at several points
419 throughout the day.

420 Measurements of fIPAR obtained at the same location made it possible to examine variability
421 between results obtained using a still camera and an action camera. This pointed to their potential
422 for providing a reliable and cost-effective tool for making rapid assessments. At each site, data were
423 collected over three consecutive days (3 repetitions), under clear-sky conditions (Mollerusa: April
424 17th, 18th, 19th; Raimat: May 29th, 30th, 31st, Les Borges Blanques: July 15th, 16th, 17th).
425 The commercial prices of the devices and accessories required for each approach were \$1500, for
426 the ceptometer, \$2300, for the still camera with a self-levelling support, and \$510, for the action
427 camera. The metrics of variability revealed the interactions between canopy type and temporal
428 variation throughout the day (Figure 14). The almond canopies, with their larger size and globular-
429 shaped tree crowns, exhibited much less irregularity for the different measurement approaches than
430 the apple and vineyard canopies. In contrast, canopies with a more pronounced edge arrangement,
431 such as those of apple trees and vineyards, showed greater irregularity, particularly at midday. This
432 was probably a result of the pronounced effects that the time of day and solar position had on the
433 interception of beams of sunlight in the case of these narrower canopies. In the case of photographs
434 and videos, the presumed radiation pattern for direct and diffuse components remained
435 constant. However, irregularity in fIPAR from photos and videos occurred from possible changes in
436 the area sampled over the three days of data collection, which could have been associated with
437 different start and end points in the sampling area.

438

4. General Discussion:

439 The study presents and validates a new methodology which specifically addresses the task of
440 providing a representative assessment of diurnal fIPAR for tree crops and vines. Ceptometers are
441 currently the main instruments used for assessing fIPAR in horticulture. However, providing an
442 assessment of representative fIPAR for a whole day with a ceptometer would be very labour
443 intensive and would require clear-sky conditions for the whole diurnal time window. Specialized
444 tools for making canopy measurements have been developed recently, which include devices for
445 estimating LAI and fIPAR. Tools such as the CI-110 Plant Canopy Imager (CID Bio-Science,
446 Washington, USA) provide accurate, non-destructive measurements of canopy structure and light
447 interception. While effective, these devices are often too expensive for small-scale application by
448 growers with limited resources. However, beyond economic constraints, there is a methodological
449 need to move beyond single-point measurements and toward characterizing the full diurnal
450 interception curve, which provides a more comprehensive understanding of canopy-light
451 interactions. This approach can improve the robustness of irrigation decision-making. Some of the
452 commercial devices, such as the CI-110, are based on closely related principles to those described
453 here. Rather than being viewed as alternative methods, they may in fact benefit from the insights
454 and conclusions developed in this study. In addition to advances in devices that permit the direct
455 measurement of PAR-derived parameters (such as intercepted PAR), the option of using
456 simulations based on modelling has been explored. Such models present various degrees of
457 complexity, ranging from simple models, like that proposed by Oyarzun, Stöckle and Whiting
458 (2007), to more complex ones that incorporate Radiative Transfer Models (RTM) (Guillen-Climent
459 et al., 2012). In operational terms, modelling approaches may complement but not fully replace
460 sensor-based methods, particularly in field conditions where spatial variability and rapid decision-
461 making are key.

462 On the other hand, assessments based on the approach proposed here, which uses photos taken
463 using a still camera, required less than 1 h of work per canopy, without any dependence on the time
464 of day or atmospheric conditions. The labour-saving impact of using a methodology based on
465 photography method is therefore notable and it does not require taking measurements at different
466 times of the day. This photographic approach is also much less sensitive to the time of day and
467 lighting conditions than using a ceptometer. This was shown by the fact that there were only slight
468 differences between diurnal fIPAR curves obtained under two notably different lighting conditions:
469 at dawn and mid-morning. This could have implications for practical assessments of fIPAR in
470 discontinuous canopies since the photographic method can be applied at any time of the day and
471 regardless of the cloud-cover conditions while ceptometer measurements are restricted to a narrow
472 window of daytime and weather conditions.

473 The calibration process revealed significant differences in the field of view (FOV) between the
474 fisheye-equipped still camera and the action camera. The action camera has a broader FOV,
475 particularly in photo mode, which presents advantages for canopy analysis as it captures larger
476 areas with fewer sampling points. There is, however, a trade-off between the wider FOV of the
477 action camera and some slight limitations in resolution and image distortion. These are issues that
478 must be considered, particularly when fine details of the canopy structure are required. The
479 photographic approaches proposed in this paper successfully captured diurnal patterns of fIPAR
480 across several different types of canopies. The close alignment between instantaneous fIPAR values
481 obtained using ceptometer readings and the photographic approach underscores the validity of the
482 methodology proposed here, with R^2 values consistently exceeding 0.88. Images obtained at dawn
483 were slightly better those captured during the day for segmentation and estimating fIPAR. This was
484 due to reduced interference from bright sun flares on the images and emphasizes the importance of
485 selecting appropriate sampling times based on canopy density and lighting conditions.

486 The comparison of different approaches showed that using action cameras offers an efficient and
487 cost-effective alternative to both ceptometers and still cameras. While still cameras provide high-

488 resolution images that are suitable for detailed analysis, the ability of action cameras to make
489 continuous recordings in video mode significantly reduces sampling time and enables rapid data
490 acquisition at multiple locations. The fact that action cameras are cheaper than the other alternatives
491 further emphasize their utility, especially in resource-constrained scenarios or where large-scale
492 applications are required. Furthermore, values obtained from still and action cameras showed an
493 overall correlation (Figure 13), supporting their interchangeability use in field data acquisition

494 Despite the high-level of accuracy and efficiency offered by photographic approaches, certain
495 limitations were noted. Firstly, there is the the misclassification of pixels associated with sun flares
496 in images taken under stark daylight; this remains a challenge, particularly for smaller canopies.
497 This issue could be mitigated by integrating advanced flare correction algorithms or supplementary
498 filters during image acquisition. Secondly, there is the problem of heterogeneous backgrounds.
499 Variations in anti-hail net properties and in background conditions occasionally required specific
500 adjustments to the segmentation algorithm. Adopting a more adaptable parameterization approach
501 or using machine learning-based segmentation could perhaps improve the robustness of this
502 approach and its application across a range of different environments. Finally, the irregularity
503 between repetitions in fIPAR assessment highlighted the need for standardized sampling protocols
504 to minimize any potential discrepancies arising from the use of inconsistent start and end points
505 during data collection. As this approach is largely independent of weather conditions, it offers a
506 handy and reliable tool for researchers and field operators.

507

508 5. Conclusions

509 This manuscript describes and validates a practical approach for improving the representativity of
510 vigour assessments of row crops. This is achieved by using hemispherical imaging to compute light
511 interception throughout the daytime. The approach estimates the diurnal fIPAR curve by tracking

512 the sun's path using hemispherical images or video frames. These are captured with an upward-
513 facing camera placed at different positions between the trees to record the canopy from below.

514 The methodology was tested using two setups: a still camera mounted on a self-levelling support
515 positioned near to the ground and an action camera recording short samples of video footage, held
516 on a selfie stick.

517 Firstly, this study demonstrates that using a still camera equipped with a fisheye lens and a self-
518 levelling support, set up near the ground, can offer a rigorous characterization of the pattern of
519 canopy radiation interception. This approach achieved a level of precision of 92% when used to
520 calculate the radiation interception profile. It required specialized equipment and a certain level of
521 labour input but provided highly accurate data. The study also highlights the fact that short videos
522 obtained using an action camera provide a feasible alternative to other approaches. Although
523 slightly less precise, this approach achieved an accuracy of 88%. It provides results that are
524 sufficiently reliable for most practical applications in horticulture and irrigation management.
525 Moreover, it offers an accessible and scalable option for widespread use.

526 The proposed methodology proved to offer a practical alternative to using ceptometer-based
527 measurements to assess canopy traits in discontinuous canopies such as those found in vineyards
528 and orchards. Although ceptometers are commonly used for assessing crop vigour at midday, a
529 single measurement taken at that time may not accurately represent the interception pattern for a
530 whole day. To capture a diurnal fIPAR curve using ceptometers, measurements would need to be
531 taken under clear-sky conditions at multiple times during the day. This would not only require
532 suitable weather conditions but also require a significant input of human labour. In contrast, the
533 hemispherical imaging approach described in this study requires only 10 minutes per assessment
534 and can be applied under a broad range of sky conditions and at any time of the day, making this a
535 practical and cost-saving solution.

536 This methodology is particularly valuable when it is necessary to compare orchards with different
537 training systems. Furthermore, it can be applied beneath crop protection structures, such as anti-hail
538 nets, where obtaining traditional ceptometer measurements may be compromised due to the
539 difficulty of assessing incoming solar radiation below a net.

540 Each camera-based method has its strengths depending on the context. The still camera provides
541 greater accuracy. It is also the most suitable under controlled conditions, such as overcast skies or
542 predefined measurement patterns, where light conditions are stable and variability is minimal or
543 predictable. On the other hand, the action camera provides a more practical solution for rapid
544 assessments under real-world conditions, as it offers ease of use combined with an acceptable
545 degree of precision. This flexibility highlights the potential for a wider application of this approach
546 in precision agriculture and irrigation management.

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558 **Authors Contributions:**

559 **Conceptualization:** J.C, A.E **Methodology:** J.C, M.I.B **Field work and data collection:** M.I.B,
560 J.C **Software and Image processing:** J.C, M.I.B **Validation and formal analysis:** M.I.B **Writing-**
561 **original draft:** M.I.B **Writing-reviewing and editing:** J.C, A.E, M.I.B **Supervision:** J.C, A.E

562 **Data availability:**

563 Data will be made available on request.

564 **Conflicts of interest:**

565 The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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1 **Figure 1.** fIPAR sensing devices employed (left column) with their corresponding sampling
2 patterns (right column)

3 **Figure 2.** Example of some of the challenges to canopy analysis posed by background factors, such
4 as different coloured anti-hail nets and pixels affected by sun flares.

5 **Figure 3.** Sun curve parameters (angle of the azimuth γ and elevation h_s), from Masters (2004).

6 **Figure 4.** Example of a diurnal curve of fIPAR obtained from a photo taken using a still camera on
7 an almond orchard with tree rows oriented 30° North. It shows: (a) the rectangles that defined the
8 area analysed that followed the path of the sun; (b) a mirror image of the area of analysis; (c) the
9 $fIPAR_{beam}$ for the area analysed; (d) the $fIPAR_{beam}$ for the mirror image of the area analysed; (e) the
10 average fIPAR; and (f) $PIR_{instantaneous}$ (W/m^2).

11 **Figure 5.** Board configuration for camera calibration (left). Images taken by the still camera (a) and
12 by the action camera (b).

13 **Figure 6.** Relationship between the angle of observation (in degrees) and the distances (in pixels)
14 for the still camera (a) and action camera in SuperView mode (b) and WideAngle mode (c)

15 **Figure 7.** Sample images from a still camera (photographs) and an action camera (video frames)
16 showing different canopies. In the action camera image, the video mode was set to *Wide Angle* for
17 apple trees but to *SuperView* for almond trees and vineyards.

18 **Figure 8.** Percentage of the area affected by sun flares by dataset.

19 **Figure 9.** Correction of thresholding process for yellow anti-hail nets: (a) original image with anti-
20 hail net interference, (b) initial segmented image with the anti-hail net misclassified as part of the
21 canopy, and (c) corrected image, after adjustment of thresholding procedure.

22 **Figure 10.** Regression between fIPAR from diurnal hemispherical imaging and instantaneous
23 ceptometer measurements, comparing dawn and daylight images for four canopies.

24

25 **Figure 11.** Diurnal evolution of fIPAR for the four canopies studied, organised by sampling time
26 (daylight represented by the straight line and dawn by the dashed line) vs Ceptometer measurements
27 (shown by dots), and canopy (L: Large, S: Small).

28 **Figure 12.** Relationship between fIPAR sampled at dawn and fIPAR during daylight hours (fIPAR
29 corresponding to a still camera for daylight hours, and fIPAR corresponding to a still camera at
30 dawn).

31 **Figure 13.** Relationship between estimations of fIPAR obtained using a still camera and an action
32 camera.

33 **Figure 14.** Diurnal fIPAR curves obtained using a still camera (continuous line) and an action
34 camera (dashed line) for almond (a), apple (b), and grapevine (c) canopies.

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Ceptometer

Still camera

Action camera

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Preprint not peer reviewed

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Still camera

Action camera

Apples

Almonds

Vineyard

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(a)

(b)

(c)

